

Briefing #9

Top project achievements

1. A large administrative effort for the project is the compilation of the second annual project reporting for the European Commission. The 80+ pages reporting the progress of the work and compiling the overview of used resources, is both a good control point as well as a moment for introspection on how well we are accomplishing the work we have set out to do. And all in all the feeling in the project is that we are well on track!
2. We are planning the next round of dissemination of our results. The project will be present at the EOSC Symposium in Berlin (where we will organise a project internal technical meeting), at the EUDAT Conference (Karlsruhe, December) and will organise its final Conference together with FAIR-IMPACT in the Hague 20th-21st February 2025.
3. And finally and most importantly, the progress on the implementation of our services has progressed at full steam during the summer, inter-mingled with holidaying, as the 2-3 month European holiday season has meant a lull in meetings and travels. Much concrete progress has been made in the services' development."

Technical updates

After an intensive spring of creating awareness of our work through participation in meetings such as the EOSC Winter School, euroCRIS, PIDfest and EUNIS conferences, the focus has been in the summer on development work. The service development in FAIRCORE4EOSC is taking large steps as we have roughly 6 months to the final releases of our services. Technical and user requirements are gradually being met more and more. On the administrative side, as the technical reporting is finished, we take up developing sustainability plans for our services for planning the road ahead. A quick summary of some recent developments:

- The vocabulary tool has now been integrated with a handle (PID) provider and has better SKOS import and export
- The Compliance Assessment Toolkit is adding new features and working on applying it to case studies. Work on building a Knowledge Base continues.
- RDGraph has been working on the integration of RAiD, NL search and the community recommendations in the RDGraph portals.
- PIDGraph has worked on improving the performance of PIDGraph APIs, integration of RAiD into PIDGraph and developed the provision of the PIDGraph data dumps.
- The Data Type Registry is preparing to launch a production instance with production environment Handles as well as developing the user guidance materials.
- The Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry has developed assigning DTR types to schema properties, support for many-to-one and one-to-many mappings including some basic functions. The first instances of XSLT and RML crosswalk operationalisations can be demonstrated. Integration of the EOSC Beyond test AAI has been set up, and preparations are underway to bring MSCR into the production environment.

- RAiD development has focused on the development of the RAiD access/administration framework and is turning its attention to near and medium term operational planning.
- In the PID Meta Resolver the number of incorporated providers has recently increased. Progress is made in the logging of the requests. Sustainability of the service is being explored.
- The various subcomponents of RSAC proceed independently.
- InvenioRDM RSAC is in final tests before MVP moves to production.
- DANS RSAC is in testing of the deposit integration.
- Dagstuhl RSAC component is now in production for the Archive & Reference part.
- Episciences in production and documented

Case Study Progress

The Maths case study (CS) team has continued the development of the necessary components to expose articles and software metadata in DataCite formats. The articles have been processed and exposed on the OAI-PMH server of the MaRDI infrastructure, which will be later ingested in the PIDGraph once DataCite validates the final mapping. In parallel, similar work was initiated to comply with the OpenAIRE guideline based on the current work made for the PIDGraph to ingest the metadata in the RDGraph. In link with the WP6, the team also advanced the work to expose the metadata of the swMATH software into the CodeMeta vocabulary so they can be later deposited on the Software Heritage archival services. Furthermore, they met in September with the MSCR team to confirm and specify their needs to expose metadata mappings.

The Social Sciences and Humanities CS team has deployed the Digital Object gateway with DTR Taxonomy integration in beta and has worked on further improving the service and this integration. On

the Virtual Collection registry side development work on the MSCR integration has continued and work has started to now implement the DTR integration via the Digital Object Gateway beta API. Furthermore the team started to explore in detail how they can extend the DOI metadata associated with virtual collections to improve our PIDGraph integration.

The Climate Change CS team continued implementation and coordination work to enable the use of RAiD, DTR, PIDGraph and MSCR. RAiD creation for community projects and related objects was further tested. The usefulness of the DTR profile type as a community profile was implemented and verified. Using exemplary DOI RAiD links as a PIDGraph simulation, the provenance of selected datasets was extended in terms of research area and project affiliation. In conjunction with the development of the DTR community profile, preliminary work has begun to integrate this DTR profile into an FDO object together with the DKRZ FDO forum team, with the intention of preparing a practical example of an actionable FDO in Earth System Science.

The European Integration of National-level services CS team has focused on developing further the integration of the following components: PIDGraph, MSCR, RAiD, RDGraph, SWHM. PIDGraph work on integration process has been discussed with the component team, with possible inclusion of Crossref DOI's in the data dump to better match Research.fi metadata on publications. For MSCR, the CS team has focused on making a crosswalk between Research.fi and CERIF2

a reality within the component. RAiD integration is waiting for Research.fi data model to be enhanced and Research.fi frontend development to move forwards regarding the projects so further integration would be made possible. Discussions are ongoing with RDGraph to explore its possibilities to enrich abstract information within Research.fi and to identify Finnish affiliated datasets. For SWHM, initial testing of their API has been finished and to be followed with discussions with the component team to agree on next steps.

The EOSC service providers and RDM communities CS team has created type descriptions for metadata elements of EUDAT Extended metadata schema into DTR. They have been investigating the best way to utilise existing and new features of MSCR in EUDAT B2SHARE service. It was decided that CAT would only be used through integration of EUDAT B2SHARE service to B2HANDLE service; to validate B2HANDLE service's conformance of EOSC PID Policy. EUDAT B2SHARE will then receive compliance assurances of its PID usage. The best way to utilise RDGraph in EUDAT B2SHARE is being investigated.

Besides, WP7 prepared 5 sets of high-level slides to showcase the benefits of using integrated project's components for our Case Studies communities.